

Registration Protocol: Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis

1. Review Title:

Comparative Effectiveness of Unilateral Biportal Endoscopic TLIF and Minimally Invasive TLIF in Managing Lumbar Degenerative Pathology: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis.

2. Review Question:

In adult patients with symptomatic lumbar degenerative disease requiring transforaminal lumbar interbody fusion (TLIF), does Unilateral Biportal Endoscopic TLIF (UBE-TLIF), compared to Minimally Invasive TLIF (MIS-TLIF) performed via a tubular retractor, lead to differences in clinical outcomes (pain, function), radiological outcomes (fusion rates), perioperative metrics (operative time, blood loss, hospital stay), and safety profiles (complication rates)?

PICO Framework:

- **P (Population):** Adult patients (>18 years) diagnosed with symptomatic lumbar degenerative disease (including lumbar spinal stenosis, degenerative spondylolisthesis Meyerding Grade I-II, isthmic spondylolisthesis, recurrent disc herniation, or degenerative disc disease with associated instability) indicated for single or two-level TLIF.
- **I (Intervention):** Unilateral Biportal Endoscopic Transforaminal Lumbar Interbody Fusion (UBE-TLIF), including synonymous terms like ULIF or BETLIF.
- **C (Comparison):** Minimally Invasive Transforaminal Lumbar Interbody Fusion (MIS-TLIF) performed specifically via a tubular retractor system.
- **O (Outcomes):** As detailed in sections 8 and 9 below.

3. Searches:

A comprehensive and systematic electronic literature search will be performed across four major international databases: PubMed/MEDLINE, Embase, SCOPUS, and the Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials (CENTRAL).

- **Search Dates:** The search will encompass publications from January 1st, 2015, through September 1st, 2025. This start date is chosen to capture the contemporary literature following the widespread establishment of MIS-TLIF and the emergence and refinement of UBE-TLIF techniques.
- **Search Strategy:** The strategy will combine Medical Subject Headings (MeSH), Emtree terms, and relevant free-text keywords related to the intervention (UBE-TLIF), the comparison (MIS-TLIF), and the condition (lumbar degenerative disease). Boolean operators (AND, OR) will be used to combine terms appropriately. An example search string for PubMed is planned as: `((("Endoscopy"[Mesh]) OR "Unilateral Biportal Endoscopy"[tiab] OR "UBE"[tiab] OR "Biportal Endoscopic"[tiab])) AND ((("Spinal Fusion"[Mesh]) OR "Transforaminal Lumbar Interbody Fusion"[tiab] OR "TLIF"[tiab])) AND ((("Minimally Invasive Surgical Procedures"[Mesh]) OR "Minimally Invasive"[tiab] OR "MIS"[tiab] OR "Tubular"[tiab]) AND ((("Lumbar Vertebrae"[Mesh]) OR "Spinal`

Stenosis"[Mesh] OR "Spondylolisthesis"[Mesh] OR "Intervertebral Disc Degeneration"[Mesh] OR "Lumbar Degenerative"[tiab]) (Similar strategies adapted for syntax will be used for Embase, SCOPUS, and CENTRAL).

- **Additional Search Methods:** The reference lists of all included studies and relevant systematic reviews identified during the search will be manually screened ("snowballing") to identify potentially missed publications.
- **Language Restrictions:** No language restrictions will be applied during the initial search phase. However, for practical reasons related to data extraction, only studies published in English or those providing sufficient English-language abstracts and data tables will be included in the final analysis. This limitation will be acknowledged.
- **Screening Process:** Two independent reviewers will screen titles and abstracts against the eligibility criteria. Full texts of potentially relevant articles will be obtained and assessed independently by the same two reviewers. Disagreements will be resolved through discussion and consensus, with adjudication by a third senior reviewer if necessary.

4. Condition or Domain Being Studied:

Symptomatic lumbar degenerative disease requiring surgical intervention via transforaminal lumbar interbody fusion. This includes conditions such as lumbar spinal stenosis, degenerative spondylolisthesis (Grade I-II), isthmic spondylolisthesis, recurrent disc herniation requiring fusion, and degenerative disc disease with associated instability, primarily involving the lower lumbar spine (L3-S1).

5. Participants/Population:

- **Inclusion Criteria:**
 - Adult patients (>18 years of age).
 - Diagnosed with symptomatic lumbar degenerative disease (as defined in section 4) refractory to conservative management.
 - Undergoing primary single-level or two-level TLIF procedure.
 - Participating in a study comparing UBE-TLIF versus MIS-TLIF via tubular retractor.
- **Exclusion Criteria:**
 - Patients undergoing fusion for non-degenerative pathologies (e.g., acute trauma, tumor, infection, severe deformity requiring complex correction).
 - Patients undergoing revision surgery (unless clearly stratified data for primary surgery is available).
 - Studies focusing primarily on cervical or thoracic pathology.
 - Studies comparing UBE-TLIF only to open TLIF/PLIF without a separate MIS-TLIF (tubular) group.

6. Intervention(s), Exposure(s):

Unilateral Biportal Endoscopic Transforaminal Lumbar Interbody Fusion (UBE-TLIF). This technique involves utilizing two independent portals (viewing and working) under continuous saline irrigation, without a fixed retractor system, to perform neural decompression, discectomy, endplate preparation, interbody cage insertion, and typically supplemented with percutaneous

pedicle screw fixation. Studies using synonymous terms (ULIF, BETLIF) for this specific biportal endoscopic approach will be included.

7. Comparator(s)/Control:

Minimally Invasive Transforaminal Lumbar Interbody Fusion (MIS-TLIF) performed specifically via a tubular retractor system. This technique involves a paramedian muscle-splitting approach (Wiltse plane), sequential dilation, placement of a tubular retractor, and performing the TLIF procedure (decompression, discectomy, endplate preparation, cage insertion, pedicle screw fixation) through the tube, typically under microscopic visualization. Studies comparing UBE-TLIF to MIS approaches not utilizing a tubular retractor (mini-open) will be excluded.

8. Main Outcome(s):

- **Visual Analog Scale (VAS) for Back Pain:** Measured postoperatively at early time points (direct post-op up to 3 months) and final follow-up (≥ 12 months). Mean difference (MD) will be calculated.
- **Visual Analog Scale (VAS) for Leg Pain:** Measured postoperatively at early time points (direct post-op up to 3 months) and final follow-up (≥ 12 months). Mean difference (MD) will be calculated.
- **Oswestry Disability Index (ODI):** Measured postoperatively at early time points (direct post-op up to 3 months) and final follow-up (≥ 12 months). Mean difference (MD) will be calculated.

9. Additional Outcome(s):

- **Perioperative Metrics:**
 - Operative Time (minutes): Mean difference (MD).
 - Estimated Blood Loss (EBL, mL): Mean difference (MD).
 - Postoperative Drainage Volume (mL): Mean difference (MD).
 - Length of Hospital Stay (days): Mean difference (MD).
- **Radiological Outcome:**
 - Fusion Rate (%): Assessed at final follow-up (≥ 12 months), typically using Bridwell criteria or CT evaluation (Grades I/II considered success). Risk Ratio (RR) will be calculated.
- **Safety Outcome:**
 - Overall Complication Rate (%): Incidence of any reported perioperative or postoperative complications. Risk Ratio (RR) will be calculated. Specific complications (e.g., dural tear, infection, nerve injury, implant issues) will be noted narratively.
- **Other Functional Outcomes:**
 - Health-Related Quality of Life (HRQoL) scores (SF-36, EQ-5D): Data will be extracted if reported. If sufficient homogeneity exists across studies, MD for relevant subscales (SF-36 Physical Component Summary - PCS) at final follow-up will be calculated. Otherwise, a narrative synthesis will be performed.

10. Data Extraction (Selection and Coding):

Data extraction will be performed independently by two reviewers using a pre-piloted, standardized data extraction form created in Microsoft Excel. Discrepancies will be resolved by consensus or by consulting a third reviewer. Extracted data will include:

- Study identifiers (author, year, country).
- Study characteristics (design, sample size, follow-up).
- Patient demographics (age, sex, BMI, diagnosis, levels).
- Intervention/Comparison details (specific nuances if reported).
- Outcome data for all primary and secondary outcomes (mean, SD, N for continuous; events, N for dichotomous).
- Quality assessment data (NOS scores).
- Information regarding funding and conflicts of interest.

For continuous data reported as median/IQR or range, validated methods will be used to estimate mean and SD, provided the assumptions of these methods are reasonably met.

11. Risk of Bias (Quality) Assessment:

The methodological quality and risk of bias of included studies will be independently assessed by two reviewers.

- For **Randomized Controlled Trials (RCTs)** (if identified): The Cochrane Risk of Bias tool 2 (RoB 2) will be used.
- For **Observational Cohort Studies**: The Newcastle-Ottawa Scale (NOS) will be used, assessing selection, comparability, and outcome ascertainment. Studies scoring ≥ 7 stars will be considered high quality.

Disagreements in quality assessment will be resolved through discussion and consensus. The results of the quality assessment will be presented in a table and considered in interpreting the overall findings and performing sensitivity analyses (excluding studies with high risk of bias).

12. Strategy for Data Synthesis:

Quantitative synthesis (meta-analysis) will be performed using Review Manager (RevMan) software.

- **Pooling Method**: A random-effects model (DerSimonian and Laird method) will be used for all outcomes due to anticipated clinical and methodological heterogeneity.
- **Effect Measures**: Mean Difference (MD) with 95% CIs for continuous outcomes; Risk Ratio (RR) with 95% CIs for dichotomous outcomes.
- **Heterogeneity Assessment**: Heterogeneity will be assessed using the Chi-square test ($P < 0.10$ indicating significant heterogeneity) and quantified using the I^2 statistic (<40% low, 40-75% moderate, >75% high heterogeneity).

- **Interpretation:** Pooled results will be presented using forest plots. Statistical significance will be set at $P < 0.05$ for effect estimates. The clinical significance of the findings will also be considered alongside statistical significance. Findings with high, unexplained heterogeneity will be interpreted with caution.
- **Narrative Synthesis:** If quantitative pooling is inappropriate (due to excessive heterogeneity or insufficient data for an outcome like SF-36), a narrative synthesis of the findings will be provided.

13. Analysis of Subgroups or Subsets:

- **Pre-planned Subgroup Analyses:** If significant heterogeneity ($I^2 > 75\%$) is detected, particularly for perioperative outcomes, subgroup analyses will be conducted based on:
 - Study Design (RCTs vs. Observational Studies) - if RCTs are found.
 - Geographical Location (Asian vs. Non-Asian studies) - if sufficient geographical diversity is found.
- **Exploratory (Post Hoc) Subgroup Analyses:** If substantial heterogeneity persists and data allow, exploratory analyses may be considered based on:
 - Surgical Complexity (Single-level vs. Studies including Multi-level fusion).
 - Proxy for Surgeon Experience (e.g., stratifying by publication year or stated surgeon experience if reported consistently).
- **Sensitivity Analyses:**
 - "Leave-one-out" analysis will be performed for primary outcomes to assess the influence of individual studies.
 - Analysis restricted to high-quality studies (e.g., NOS score ≥ 7) will be considered if appropriate.

14. Contact Details for Further Information:

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15. Organizational Affiliation of the Review:

Phlox Institute: Indonesian Medical Research Organization

16. Review Team Members and Their Affiliations:

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17. Anticipated or Actual Start Date:

[June 25, 2025]

18. Anticipated Completion Date:

[July 21, 2025]

19. Funding Sources/Sponsors:

None

20. Conflicts of Interest:

None

21. Language:

English

22. Country:

Indonesia

23. Stage of Review:

Review Completed